

Transformation model of scientific and technological achievement

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Introduction

Scientific and technological achievements (STA) refer to the achievements with practical value generated through science discover and technological development. STA transformation refers to the STA forming a product and exerting market value after a series of development activities. Promoting the transformation of STA is a key link to strengthen the integration of science, technology and the economy, a fundamental way to encourage scientific and technological innovation to serve the social development. However, there is still a lot of uncertain factors as to whether it can achieve the process from innovation to product and market to obtain the economic value (Dong, Xu & Wei).

In many fields, there are still some bottlenecks, such as weak collaborative innovation among scientific research institutes, universities, and industries; poor channels for knowledge diffusion and technology transfer; unconnected technological innovation and industrialization innovation chains and low transformation and implementation rate of scientific research result. Therefore, it is urgent to analyse the status quo from multiple perspectives, clarify the general process and rules of these phenomena, and discover the key crux of the issue and prescribe the right medicine.

Research Status

The interaction between STI is not simple and linear involving many subjects and elements. Jiang discussed in detail the relationship between the scientific revolution, the technological revolution and the industrial revolution. He considered the scientific revolution was the precursor of the technological revolution, and that the technological revolution was the inevitable result of the scientific revolution; the technological revolution was the precursor of the industrial revolution, and industrial revolution was the inevitable result of the technological revolution. In addition to this positive effect, there is also reverse effect between STI.

The three revolutions are a dialectic development that is closely linked and interacting (Jiang, 1992);

Some researchers also considered the three revolution as an organic whole, and carried out specific research on this system from the aspects of constituent elements, system structure, association mechanism and evolution process (Xu et al., 2022), which essentially reflects the complex and interactive relationship among STI that intertwines and promotes mutually.

As shown in Figure 1, in a positive innovation system, STI are intertwined to promote, integrate and response with each other along the time axis, presenting a three-spiral innovation evolution way. In t Fig.1, t is the time axis, the yellow curve represents the progress direction of scientific, the green curve represents the progress direction of technological progress, the blue curve represents the direction of industrial development, and the line between the curves represents the knowledge relationship between the three.

Figure 1. Three-spiral evolution mode of STI

It should be noted that in the real scene of social development, the benign interaction of knowledge is not realized between STI in many fields. The knowledge relationship between the three is usually weak, which may be the root cause of poor, unsmooth, and unsuccessful transformation from science to technology and finally to the real productivity.

Methodology

The main goal of this article is to realize the quantification, automation and visual recognition of STA transformation modes, to comprehensively measure the knowledge transformation capabilities of different modes. To achieve this goal, this article proposes a method of the STA transformation model

based on STI knowledge linkage. As shown in Figure 2, it mainly includes three parts:

Figure 2. framework for transformation mode of STA

Analysis idea

Detection model of STI knowledge linkage. Research papers and patent literature were used to characterize scientific research and technology research, and product literature to represent industry development knowledge, we calculate topic linkage, determine topic distribution time based on accurately identifying three types of STI topics, and construct an automated detection model of STI knowledge linkage in a quantitative, automated, and visualized manner.

Transformation models of STA

According to the existing theoretical foundation, the industrialization process of technological achievements is irreversible. Therefore, the case where related topics are distributed on the industrial path without being on the technological path does not exist theoretically, and the time when related topics are distributed on the technical path must precede the distribution of time on the industrial path.

Empirical analysis

Data source

Gene Engineered Vaccine (GEV) is the main component of new vaccine types, and it is also a key development branch in the field of biomedicine. This

article selects the GEV field as the object of empirical analysis.

STA transformation mode

The recognition result of the STA transformation pattern in phase 3 is shown in Figure 3. The main modes are S mode, T mode, S-T mode / T-S mode, and T-S-I mode.

Figure 3 Transformation mode of STA in phase 3

Conclusion and discussion

The text-based STI knowledge linkage analysis provides a new method for the research of STA transformation mode, but its effectiveness and feasibility need further discussion. In terms of effectiveness, there are currently no directly relevant data analysis results that can be compared with the research results of this article, so this article mainly investigates the current status of related research and practice development in the GEV field, and discusses the effects of empirical analysis in the GEV field with expert opinions.

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